

Corpus-based Automatic Identification of Multi-word Entry Candidates

Pavel Rychlý, Miloš Jakubíček

Natural Language Processing Centre
Faculty of Informatics, Masaryk University
{pary, jak}@fi.muni.cz

Lexical Computing
{pavel.rychly, milos.jakubicek}@sketchengine.eu

Abstract.

In this paper we present a corpus-based approach for automatic identification of multi-word expressions that are suitable for dictionary inclusion in the form of standalone entries.

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1 Introduction

One of the first but key decisions to make when building a dictionary is deciding which headwords should go into the dictionary to form the dictionary entries. Modern dictionaries are corpus-based: given the target dictionary size being n entries, one retrieves the n most frequent words¹ in a corpus as a primary data source. The editors go through the list and remove unwanted items (e.g. spelling errors) depending on some editorial guidelines.

This all works fine for single-word entries. How about multi-word entries, though? Multi-word expressions represent a very challenging topic for both linguistics and natural language processing. The questions in these scientific fields that remain unanswered are:

1. what are multi-word expressions? (linguistics)
2. how to find them automatically? (NLP)

Needless to say, the answer to the NLP question gets frequently stuck because of the linguistic question being unanswered too.

In the (more practical) context of lexicography the key question is utilitarianistically simple: which multi-word expressions should form standalone entries in the dictionary?² In case of a general language dictionary³, the answer to this

¹ In practice one uses better counts than mere frequency counts, e.g. document counts.

² When saying standalone entries we disregard any particular entry structure – the multi-words might not be entries but only entry parts of course.

³ Unlike e.g. a domain-specific glossary

question is primarily led by Frege’s principle of compositionality: if the meaning of the multi-word cannot be easily derived from the meaning of its components by the reader, the multi-word needs to be put into the dictionary to be explained.

In this paper we present a way of finding multi-words satisfying such non-compositionality principle.

2 How to find non-compositional multi-words

Single-word items are found by counting words. The same approach obviously doesn’t work for multi-words: generating most frequent n-grams yields all but lexicographically interesting data because mere n-gram counts do not relate to the non-compositionality requirement in any way.

For the sake of simplicity we make two restrictions in the following text:

- we consider only two-word expressions
- we consider only continuous expressions (bigrams)

It should be emphasized though that the underlying algorithm can be extended to expressions consisting of more than two words and that the requirement for continuousness can be lifted when using more advanced methods for collocation discovery like e.g. word sketches [1].

We build upon the assumption that word meaning is defined by a word’s context and therefore to discover non-compositional two-word expressions we compare the usage context of the two components and of the multi-word itself. If they differ significantly it is a good sign that the meaning might be non-compositional. We do not provide any thresholds but calculate a score that can be used to generate sorted multi-word candidates for a lexicographer to consider.

3 Multi-word scoring

A typical way of scoring a multi-word in lexicography is applying a lexicographic association score such as logDice [2]. Scores like this are however based on mere frequency of the multi-word components and while they serve very well the purpose of identifying strength of the association, i.e. collocation, they cannot be used to assess the compositionality.

In Tables 1 and 2 we give collocations for the English adjective *black* and noun *hole* to demonstrate this. In Table 1 one can see that *black hair* has higher logDice score than *black box* which is correct because hair is less frequent than *box* while *black hair* is more frequent than *black box*, thus the association is strong for *hair* than for *box*. But black hair is fully compositional while *black box* is obviously not. This goes similarly for *watering hole* and *rabbit hole* in Table 2.

To assess the non-compositionality we therefore compare the context of the multi-word bigram with the contexts of its both components. Given a bigram multi-word *AB* consisting of words *A* and *B*, *x* being the first word to the left

Word	Cooccurrence count	Candidate count	T-score	MI-score	logDice
hole	8,971	84,121	94.613	9.861	9.323
hair	4,075	160,711	63.547	7.788	7.962
box	2,539	207,760	49.915	6.735	7.158
leather	1,732	31,062	41.531	8.925	7.127
pepper	1,610	18,778	40.071	9.546	7.066
market	3,810	567,502	60.671	5.871	7.049
man	7,183	1,448,573	82.792	5.434	7.012
voters	1,696	121,757	40.843	6.924	6.806

Table 1. Collocations of the adjective *black*, sorted by logDice. Data calculated on the first billion of the enTenTen 2008 corpus [3].

Word	Cooccurrence count	Candidate count	T-score	MI-score	logDice
black	8,970	374,781	94.608	9.861	9.323
gaping	824	4,925	28.700	12.666	8.244
ozone	879	17,014	29.633	10.971	8.153
watering	735	7,484	27.103	11.897	8.038
rabbit	505	13,755	22.456	10.478	7.401
bullet	391	30,475	19.734	8.961	6.804
drilled	287	7,361	16.929	10.565	6.683

Table 2. Collocations of the noun *hole*, sorted by logDice. Data calculated on the first billion of the enTenTen 2008 corpus [3].

and y being the first word to the right, then for every x and y we calculate counts of xAB , xA , xB and ABy , Ay and By .

Shall the multi-word bigram behave compositionally, there should be a high overlap for each x between xAB and either xA or xB , and similarly for every y between ABy and Ay or By . For *black hair*, the collocate *shiny* would go with *black hair* just as it goes with *black* and the collocate *curly* would go with *black hair* just as it goes with *hair*.

We measure this overlap by taking the average *keyness* over all x and y . The keyness is calculated as the maximum of two ratios p/q and q/p , where p and q are relative collocation (cooccurrence) counts of the bigram multi-word and the single word, respectively. This way we calculate a score, the higher it is, the higher the non-compositionality would be.

In Tables 3 and 4 we give results for the adjective *black* and noun *hole* which show that the score corresponds with the desired outcomes.

4 Conclusions

In this paper we have presented a novel method for identifying multi-word expressions that should be put as entries into dictionary because of their non-compositionality. The method requires a reasonably large corpus to work well (the multi-word should have hundreds of counts at least). We have demonstrated

Bigram multi-word	Score
black pepper	23.5
black box	11.5
black market	11.4
black hole	8.2
black leather	4.6
black hair	3.0
black voters	2.4
black man	2.2

Table 3. Results for the adjective *black* and selected bigram words.

Bigram multi-word	Score
watering hole	15.9
ozone hole	14.2
black hole	8.2
rabbit hole	2.2
gaping hole	1.9
bullet hole	1.8
drilled hole	1.2

Table 4. Results for the noun *hole* and selected bigram words.

how it work and an example of multi-word bigrams, further work is required to extend the functionality to multi-words of any length.

References

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